

Damping formulation for viscoelastic composite materials and structures, using the complex energy concept

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ABSTRACT

For linear viscoelastic composite materials under harmonic loading, a complex energy $w^* = w + i \frac{\Delta w}{2\pi}$ is defined, where w represents the mean elastic energy and Δw represents the energy dissipated over a cycle. Using the complex energy conservation theorem, it is shown that energy methods, analogous to those used for elasticity, are available. The energies w and Δw are expressed as quadratic hermitean forms of the strain (or stress) tensors, and accurate expressions for the dissipated energy involving the specific damping capacity matrix are derived. A numerical example of a S.D.C. matrix (unidirectional carbon/epoxy) is presented.

Keywords : viscoelasticity, damping, carbon/epoxy composites, energy methods.

1. INTRODUCTION

Using composite materials in structures subjected to severe cyclic loads (e.g. : non-rigid robot arms, torque shafts, airplane wing units, ...) increasingly raises the problem of how to compute the damping of such materials, so as to predict (and minimize) the vibration amplitude of the whole structure. Many composite materials with organic matrix (e.g. carbon/epoxy or glass/epoxy) exhibit linear viscoelastic behaviour at low strain, thus allowing the effective complex moduli theory to be used [1]. Although this theory available for viscoelastic media is quite similar to that used for elasticity (correspondence principle based on the Fourier transform), little use has been made of energy methods for viscoelasticity. We presume that the reason for this lies in the absence of a unique and adequate definition of energy for a viscoelastic material under cyclic loading [2]. The purpose of this paper is to build up such a definition in order to extend the use of energy methods to linear viscoelastic materials under cyclic loading, concerning in particular damping of composite materials and structures.

2. ENERGY DEFINITIONS

2.1. Dissipated energy and stored energy

Let us consider a small volume element - figure 1- subjected to a three-dimensional harmonic loading. In permanent state, the stresses σ_i^* and strains ϵ_i^* ($i = 1$ to 6) are harmonic functions of time :

$$\{\sigma_i^*(t)\} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11}^* \\ \sigma_{22}^* \\ \sigma_{33}^* \\ \sigma_{23}^* \\ \sigma_{31}^* \\ \sigma_{12}^* \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1^* \\ \sigma_2^* \\ \sigma_3^* \\ \sigma_4^* \\ \sigma_5^* \\ \sigma_6^* \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \{\varepsilon_i^*(t)\} = \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{11}^* \\ \varepsilon_{22}^* \\ \varepsilon_{33}^* \\ 2\varepsilon_{23}^* \\ 2\varepsilon_{31}^* \\ 2\varepsilon_{12}^* \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_1^* \\ \varepsilon_2^* \\ \varepsilon_3^* \\ \varepsilon_4^* \\ \varepsilon_5^* \\ \varepsilon_6^* \end{pmatrix}$$

with: $\sigma_i^*(t) = \sigma_i^{\circ} \cdot e^{i\omega t}$ $\sigma_i^{\circ} \in \mathbb{C}$ where: $\sigma_i^{\circ} = \sigma_i^{\circ'} + i \cdot \sigma_i^{\circ''} = |\sigma_i^{\circ}| \cdot e^{i\varphi_i}$
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Figure 1. Dissipated and stored energies of a volume element (linear viscoelastic)

Let us call Δw the energy dissipated over a period per volume unit, which is represented by the sum of the six areas of the hysteretic loops in figure 1, or by the following quadratic hermitean forms :

$$\Delta w = \pi \cdot \bar{\varepsilon}_i^{\circ} \cdot C_{ij}^{\circ} \cdot \varepsilon_j^{\circ} = -\pi \cdot \bar{\sigma}_i^{\circ} \cdot S_{ij}^{\circ} \cdot \sigma_j^{\circ} \quad (1)$$

where Einstein's implicit summation rule is employed from here on, with subscripts i and j varying from 1 to 6. In equation 1 above:

* $\overline{\sigma_i^{\circ}} = \sigma_i^{\circ'} - i \cdot \sigma_i^{\circ''}$ and $\overline{\epsilon_i^{\circ}} = \epsilon_i^{\circ'} - i \cdot \epsilon_i^{\circ''}$ are the complex conjugates of ϵ_i° and σ_i° .

* C_{ij}'' and S_{ij}'' are the imaginary parts of the effective complex moduli and compliance matrices,

respectively defined by :

$$\sigma_i^{\circ} = C_{ij}^* \cdot \epsilon_j^{\circ} \quad C_{ij}^* = C_{ij}' + i \cdot C_{ij}''$$

$$\epsilon_i^{\circ} = S_{ij}^* \cdot \sigma_j^{\circ} \quad S_{ij}^* = S_{ij}' + i \cdot S_{ij}''$$

Let us call $w/2$ the mean elastic energy per volume unit (calculated over a period), which is represented by the sum of the six areas of the shaded triangles in figure 1, where the upper right apexes are defined as the points of maximum stress (vertical tangent). Alternatively, triangles having the same area may be defined by taking the upper right apexes as the points of maximum strain (horizontal tangent).

Note that w is defined as *twice the mean elastic energy*, rather than the maximum elastic energy. In fact, the latter definition would require knowing the complex modulus over the whole range of frequencies (i.e. the rheological model), whilst the former only depends on the complex moduli at the current frequency ω [3].

We obtain the expression of w by integrating the free energy (Helmholtz) $\rho \cdot A$ over a period, assuming isothermal viscoelasticity [4] :

$$w = \int_{\tau} \rho \cdot A(t) \cdot dt$$

The thermodynamic and rheological justifications of the above definition as well as the demonstration of equation (2) hereafter using the Volterra series expansion of free energy will be published elsewhere. Finally, integration yields :

$$2 \cdot w = \overline{\epsilon_i^{\circ}} \cdot C_{ij}' \cdot \epsilon_j^{\circ} = \overline{\sigma_i^{\circ}} \cdot S_{ij}' \cdot \sigma_j^{\circ} \quad (2)$$

The following formulas are derived from equations (1) and (2) :

$$\Delta w = -\pi \left[\sigma_i^{\circ'} \cdot \epsilon_i^{\circ''} - \sigma_i^{\circ''} \cdot \epsilon_i^{\circ'} \right] \quad 2 \cdot w = \sigma_i^{\circ'} \cdot \epsilon_i^{\circ'} + \sigma_i^{\circ''} \cdot \epsilon_i^{\circ''}$$

$$\Delta w = -\pi \left[\sigma_i^{\circ'} \cdot S_{ij}'' \cdot \sigma_j^{\circ'} + \sigma_i^{\circ''} \cdot S_{ij}'' \cdot \sigma_j^{\circ''} \right] \quad 2 \cdot w = \sigma_i^{\circ'} \cdot S_{ij}' \cdot \sigma_j^{\circ'} + \sigma_i^{\circ''} \cdot S_{ij}' \cdot \sigma_j^{\circ''}$$

$$\Delta w = \pi \left[\epsilon_i^{\circ'} \cdot C_{ij}'' \cdot \epsilon_j^{\circ'} + \epsilon_i^{\circ''} \cdot C_{ij}'' \cdot \epsilon_j^{\circ''} \right] \quad 2 \cdot w = \epsilon_i^{\circ'} \cdot C_{ij}' \cdot \epsilon_j^{\circ'} + \epsilon_i^{\circ''} \cdot C_{ij}' \cdot \epsilon_j^{\circ''}$$

or stating :

$$\sigma_i^*(t) = \left| \sigma_i^{\circ} \right| \cdot e^{i(\omega t + \varphi_i)}$$

$$\epsilon_i^*(t) = \left| \epsilon_i^{\circ} \right| \cdot e^{i(\omega t + \delta_i)}$$

we obtain :

$$\Delta w = -\pi \cdot \left| \sigma_i^{\circ} \right| \cdot \left| S_{ij}'' \right| \cdot \left| \sigma_j^{\circ} \right| \cdot \cos(\varphi_i - \varphi_j) \quad 2 \cdot w = \left| \sigma_i^{\circ} \right| \cdot \left| S_{ij}' \right| \cdot \left| \sigma_j^{\circ} \right| \cdot \cos(\varphi_i - \varphi_j)$$

$$\Delta w = \pi \cdot \left| \epsilon_i^{\circ} \right| \cdot \left| C_{ij}'' \right| \cdot \left| \epsilon_j^{\circ} \right| \cdot \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j) \quad 2 \cdot w = \left| \epsilon_i^{\circ} \right| \cdot \left| C_{ij}' \right| \cdot \left| \epsilon_j^{\circ} \right| \cdot \cos(\delta_i - \delta_j)$$

Let us now give a simpler expression of the two energies w (elastic) and Δw (dissipated), by introducing the complex energy concept.

2.2. Complex energy

Energies w and Δw are combined in a single complex number w^* :

$$w^* = w + i \cdot \frac{\Delta w}{2\pi} \quad (3)$$

that can be put into the following form :

$$w^* = \frac{\sigma_i^{\circ} \cdot \bar{\epsilon}_i^{\circ}}{2} \quad (4)$$

This expression looks like the usual expression of strain energy for elastic materials. However, the elastic stresses and strains refer to a euclidean tridimensional space E^3 where the components of displacement are real numbers, while the viscoelastic stresses and strains refer to a hermitean tridimensional space E^{3*} where the components of displacement are complex numbers representing a harmonic vibration [3].

The complex moduli theory may then be expressed in terms of energy, by using energy theorems similar to those which are currently used in elasticity, e.g. Castigliano's theorem [Ibid.] :

$$\frac{\partial w^*}{\partial \epsilon_i^{\circ}} = \sigma_i^{\circ} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial w^*}{\partial \sigma_i^{\circ}} = \bar{\epsilon}_i^{\circ}$$

Although complex energy seems to be a new concept in the field of Mechanics, it is quite familiar to electricians who usually split electrical energy into active and reactive energy. Using an electrical analogy between voltage and stress on one hand, intensity and strain rate on the other hand, the following appear :

- active energy (i.e. the energy dissipated inside a passive component such as a resistance) is analogous to the energy Δw dissipated by relaxations of the macromolecular chains inside the viscoelastic material.
- reactive energy (i.e. the energy periodically stored and released by components such as inductances and capacitances) is analogous to the energy w periodically stored and released by the reversible mechanisms inside the viscoelastic volume element.

Let us now state the complex energy conservation theorem from which we will deduce approximate computation methods available for linear viscoelastic structures under cyclic loadings.

3. THE COMPLEX ENERGY CONSERVATION THEOREM

Although a general expression of the conservation theorem available for a distributed periodic load of any shape has been established using Fourier series [3], we will consider here only the simple case of a structure D subjected to a single concentrated harmonic load, i.e. imposed force F^* or displacement U^* , such as the example shown in figure 2.

Let us name $u_i^* = u_i^{\circ} \cdot e^{i\omega t}$ the displacements of the various points of the structure, and ρ the density.

Figure 5. Example of a structure subjected to a single concentrated load.

The conservation theorem (the demonstration of which is analogous to that of the conservation theorem in elasticity) states :

$$\frac{F^* \cdot \overline{u^*}}{2} = \int_D w^* \cdot dv - \int_D \frac{\rho \cdot \omega^2 |u_i^o|^2 \cdot dv}{2} \quad (5)$$

Separation of the real and imaginary parts yields :

$$\frac{|F^o| \cdot |u^o| \cdot \cos \varphi}{2} = \int_D w \cdot dv - \int_D \frac{\rho \cdot \omega^2 |u_i^o|^2 \cdot dv}{2} \quad (6)$$

$$\pi \cdot |F^o| \cdot |u^o| \cdot \sin \varphi = \int_D \Delta w \cdot dv \quad (7)$$

where equation 7 states that the energy received by the system during a period equals the dissipated energy that can be obtained from equation 1.

The right hand side in equation 6 represents twice the difference between the mean "elastic" energy (i.e. Helmholtz free energy) and the mean kinetic energy of the system. The left hand side term results from external forces that govern the distribution between the elastic and kinetic energies during the forced vibration. We suggest calling this term "reactive energy", by analogy with electricity. Note that the reactive energy is zero in resonating conditions.

4. BASIS FOR APPROXIMATE CALCULATION METHODS

Let us assume that an arbitrary relation is given between the displacement $u^* = u^o \cdot e^{i\omega t}$ of the point(s) where external forces are applied, and the displacement $u_i^* = u_i^o \cdot e^{i\omega t}$ of every point in the structure. Thus we obtain the strain tensor $\underline{\epsilon}$ from which we derive the energies w and Δw by using equations (1) and (2). Finally, from the conservation theorem (equations 6 and 7), we obtain the modulus and argument of the unknown driving force F^* as a function of the given displacement u^* . This method will be referred to as the displacement method, and may be illustrated by the following scheme :

displacement method: $|u^o| \rightarrow \underline{\epsilon}(u^o) \rightarrow \left\{ \begin{matrix} w \\ \Delta w \end{matrix} \right\} \rightarrow F^o \left\{ \begin{matrix} \text{modulus} \\ \text{argument} \end{matrix} \right\}$

Another method - the force method - consists in assuming an arbitrary relation between the driving force F^* and the stress field $\underline{\sigma}$, thus obtaining the modulus and argument of the unknown displacement u^* by the following scheme :

force method (Adams & Bacon): $|F^o| \rightarrow \underline{\sigma}(F^o) \rightarrow \left\{ \begin{matrix} w \\ \Delta w \end{matrix} \right\} \rightarrow u^o \left\{ \begin{matrix} \text{modulus} \\ \text{argument} \end{matrix} \right\}$

The force method was first used first by R.D. Adams and D.G.C. Bacon [5] to calculate the specific damping capacity (SDC) $\psi = \Delta w/w$ of a laminate, although no accurate definition of elastic energy w was given. Assuming a plane state of stress, the authors express the energy dissipated inside a lamina (per volume unit) as :

$$\Delta w = \psi_L \cdot w_L(\sigma_L) + \psi_T \cdot w_T(\sigma_T) + \psi_{LT} \cdot w_{LT}(\sigma_{LT})$$

with: $w_L(\sigma_L) = \frac{\sigma_L^2}{2 \cdot E_L}$; $w_T(\sigma_T) = \frac{\sigma_T^2}{2 \cdot E_T}$ and $w_{LT}(\sigma_{LT}) = \frac{\sigma_{LT}^2}{2 \cdot G_{LT}}$

Figure 3. Plane state of stress in a unidirectional layer

A similar expression is obtained by expanding the quadratic form of equation (1).

$$\Delta w = \psi_{11} \cdot w_1(\sigma_1) + \psi_{22} \cdot w_2(\sigma_2) + \psi_{66} \cdot w_6(\sigma_6) + \Delta c \quad (8)$$

with:

$$\psi_{ij} = -2\pi \frac{S''_{ij}}{S'_{ij}} \quad (9)$$

$$w_1(\sigma_1) = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_1 \cdot S'_{11} \cdot \sigma_1}{2} ; \quad w_2(\sigma_2) = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_2 \cdot S'_{22} \cdot \sigma_2}{2} ; \quad w_6(\sigma_6) = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_6 \cdot S'_{66} \cdot \sigma_6}{2}$$

and:

$$\Delta c = \Delta w_{12} + \Delta w_{21} = -2\pi \cdot |\sigma_1^\circ| \cdot S''_{12} \cdot |\sigma_2^\circ| \cdot \cos(\varphi_1 - \varphi_2)$$

Hence appears an additional term Δc that was not taken into account by Adams and Bacon. For a carbon/epoxy laminate, it has been shown that this term does not exceed 10 % of the total dissipated energy. Furthermore, it is around 0.01 Δw for most states of stress, which is negligible [6]. Note that in the displacement method, the appropriate S.D.C. would be defined as :

$$\psi_{ij}^{(e)} = 2\pi \frac{C''_{ij}}{C'_{ij}} \quad (10)$$

which is different from expression (9). The latter expression only is consistent with Adams and Bacon's method.

Obyiously, the energy methods do not apply only to laminates, but are also available for any linear viscoelastic material.

In the usual case of an orthotropic material with "small" loss tangents [7], the complex compliance matrix [S'] is :

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_3 \\ \varepsilon_4 \\ \varepsilon_5 \\ \varepsilon_6 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_1' & -\nu_{12}'/E_1' & -\nu_{13}'/E_1' & & & \\ & 1/E_2' & -\nu_{23}'/E_2' & & & \\ & & 1/E_3' & & & \\ & & & 1/G_4' & & \\ \text{sym.} & & & & 1/G_5' & \\ & & & & & 1/G_6' \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 \\ \sigma_4 \\ \sigma_5 \\ \sigma_6 \end{pmatrix}$$

while the damping characteristics are expressed by the S.D.C. matrix defined by equation (9) :

$$[\Psi] = \begin{bmatrix} \Psi_{11} & \Psi_{12} & \Psi_{13} & & & \\ & \Psi_{22} & \Psi_{23} & & & \\ & & \Psi_{33} & & & \\ & & & \Psi_{44} & & \\ & \text{sym.} & & & \Psi_{55} & \\ & & & & & \Psi_{66} \end{bmatrix}$$

where diagonal Ψ_{ii} terms are positive, and other terms are usually positive [3].

Applying the force method, we obtain the S.D.C. of the volume element : $\psi = \Delta w/w$, where the energy Δw dissipated per volume unit over a period is :

$$\Delta w = \sum_{i=1}^{i=6} \Psi_{ii} \cdot w_i(\sigma_i) + \Delta c \quad (11)$$

where: $w_i(\sigma_i) = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_i \cdot S_{ij} \cdot \sigma_i}{2} \quad (i = 1 \text{ to } 6)$

and: $\Delta c = \Psi_{23} \cdot (w_{23} + w_{32}) + \Psi_{31} \cdot (w_{31} + w_{13}) + \Psi_{12} \cdot (w_{12} + w_{21})$

with: $w_{ij} + w_{ji} = |\sigma_i^\circ| \cdot S_{ij} \cdot |\sigma_j^\circ| \cdot \cos(\varphi_i - \varphi_j)$

The elastic energy w , where complex conjugate terms have been written in parenthesis, is :

$$w = \sum_{i=1}^{i=6} w_i(\sigma_i) + (w_{23} + w_{32}) + (w_{31} + w_{13}) + (w_{12} + w_{21})$$

To end with a numerical example, let us consider a thick unidirectional layer assumed to be transversely isotropic (although this is not always true, for the manufacturing process may induce transverse anisotropy). The complex compliance matrix is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_3 \\ \varepsilon_4 \\ \varepsilon_5 \\ \varepsilon_6 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_1' - \nu_{12}'/E_1' - \nu_{12}'/E_1' & & & & & \\ & 1/E_2' - \nu_{23}'/E_2' & & & & \\ & & 1/E_2' & & & \\ & & & 2(1+\nu_{23}')/E_2' & & \\ & \text{sym.} & & & 1/G_{12}' & \\ & & & & & 1/G_{12}' \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 \\ \sigma_4 \\ \sigma_5 \\ \sigma_6 \end{pmatrix}$$

and the S.D.C. matrix is :

$$[\Psi] = \begin{bmatrix} \Psi_1 & \Psi_{12} & \Psi_{12} & & & \\ & \Psi_2 & \Psi_{23} & & & \\ & & \Psi_2 & & & \\ & & & \Psi_4 & & \\ & \text{sym.} & & & \Psi_6 & \\ & & & & & \Psi_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where: $\Psi_{44} \approx \frac{\Psi_{22} + \nu_{23}' \cdot \Psi_{23}}{1 + \nu_{23}'}$ (13)

results from the equality: $S_{44}^* = 2(S_{22}^* - S_{23}^*)$ and from expressions (9) and (11). Finally, the dynamic behaviour of the transversely isotropic material is represented by ten independant real numbers : E_1 , E_2 , G_{12} , ν_{12} , ν_{13} , ψ_1 , ψ_2 , ψ_6 , ψ_{12} , and ψ_{23}

The six main coefficients E_1 , E_2 , G_{12} , ψ_1 , ψ_2 and ψ_6 were measured directly [3], while the real parts of Poisson's ratio ν_{12} and ν_{23} are assumed to be equal to the static values (which induces little error). The two last terms ψ_{12} and ψ_{23} (coupled damping capacities) have been estimated from micromechanical calculations (ibid.).

E_1	E_2	G_{12}	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	G_{23}
168 GPa	7.7 GPa	4.7 GPa	0.28	0.25	3.1 GPa
ψ_1	ψ_2	ψ_6	ψ_{12}	ψ_{23}	ψ_4
1.4%	5.7%	8.7%	3.6%	14.7%	7.5%

Table 1. Dynamic characteristics of a unidirectional carbon/epoxy (Hercules IM6 G 12K, Ciba-Geigy LH/LY 5052, $\nu_F = 0.6$, 20°C, 100 Hz).

5. CONCLUSION

It has been shown that the energy of a linear viscoelastic material under harmonic loading may be defined by a complex number. From this definition, energy theorems and approximate calculation methods using complex algebra have been derived by following a procedure analogous to elastic materials. Finally, an accurate expression of the dissipated energy involving the specific damping capacity matrix of a composite material volume element has been established, and a numerical example for a carbon/epoxy unidirectional composite has been presented.

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